

Hybridization of Differential Evolution with Reinforcement Learning and Polynomial Extrapolation in noisy problems

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Abstract. In the present paper we propose a hybrid approach of Differential Evolution algorithm in noisy optimization problems. The classical algorithm is combined with a reinforcement learning technique and polynomial extrapolation to allocate intelligently the available computational budget to promising candidate solutions, guiding the population to the global optimum by reducing the effect of noise. Experimental tests are performed on five established benchmark problems, with varying dimensionality and noise levels, and the results are statistically compared with an approach based on Particle Swarm Optimization method. Useful conclusions are derived and questions that require further investigation on both methods arise.

1 Introduction

The presence of noise in optimization of real life applications introduces the use of high performance algorithms. Evolutionary and swarm intelligence methods are a powerful set in coping with uncertainty. *Particle swarm optimization* ([1]) and *Differential Evolution* ([2]), in a simple or hybrid form, have been successfully used to solve such problems, due to their population based mechanism.

These two algorithms have been widely used in scientific and engineering applications. They have apparent structural and operational similarities, such as the use of an iteratively updated population of potential solutions, based on combination of difference vectors among existing population members. However, there is a slight, yet important difference in their mechanisms. DE uses *mutation and recombination* as its main core of updating decision vectors, while PSO retains a centralized feature of choosing the global best point and all members of the population follow this point, towards its direction, with a predefined velocity. The individuals perform subsequent evaluations of an objective function. The presence of noise can definitely transform the landscape of the function, guiding the algorithm to locally optimal solutions.

Therefore, specific techniques must be incorporated in order to ameliorate the effect of uncertainty ([3–5]). Three main categories have been introduced in coping with this issue, namely *explicit* and *implicit* averaging, as well as modifying selection, when used in evolutionary and swarm intelligence methods. They consist of averaging over multiple samples of a specific candidate solution, utilizing an increased number of individuals in the population that eliminate noise in total and using a threshold in selecting between individuals or derandomizing the selection to account for the problem noise. The most common technique in explicit averaging is equal sampling of solutions. The *Optimal Computing Budget Allocation* approach, proposed by Chen ([6]), is based on Bayesian statistics and utilizes both the mean and the variance in explicit averaging as a terms to maximize the *Probability of Correct Selection* ([5]) by calculating the number of samples-replications for each system. A superior solution can be identified either by quantifying its ranking among other solutions by using a measure such as the PCS or by taking into account differences in the fitness values using the *Expected Opportunity Cost* (EOC) [7]. The OCBA technique is initially designed for selection between different systems in simulation, where analytical solutions or a specific objective function cannot be formulated and only a complex design with stochastic output exists.

In [8], a method based on PSO method was proposed, utilizing a *reinforcement learning (RL)* approach in accordance with the PCS technique, for the efficient allocation of computational budget among individuals. We propose an extended scheme, using Differential Evolution as the core method and polynomial extrapolation incorporated into the RL algorithm in order to predict the PCS values for the next allocation.

The rest of the current paper is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the methods used in the hybrid algorithm, in Section 3 the algorithm is described in details, while in Section 4 the experimental settings and results are presented and analyzed. The paper concludes in Section 5.

2 Background Information

The noisy optimization problem, using multiplicative noise, considered throughout the paper is defined as follows:

$$\min_{x \in X \subset \mathbb{R}^n} f(x)(1 + \eta), \quad (1)$$

where $f(x)$ is the actual (noiseless) objective function defined over the search space X , and η is a Gaussian random variable:

$$\eta \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2),$$

with zero mean and standard deviation σ .

2.1 Differential Evolution

The DE algorithm was introduced by Storn and Price [2] as a population-based, stochastic optimization algorithm for numerical optimization problems. It employs a population:

$$P = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\},$$

of individuals to probe the search space. The population is randomly initialized, following a uniform distribution over the search space. Each individual is an n -dimensional vector, serving as a candidate solution of the minimization problem under consideration.

The population is evolved by applying two operators, namely *mutation* and *recombination*, for producing new candidate solutions. Then, *selection* takes place to construct a new population of potential solutions, by choosing the most promising based on the objective function values. The aforementioned operators are iteratively applied until a termination criterion is fulfilled.

The mutation operator produces a new vector, v_i , for each individual, x_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, by combining x_i with some of its mates. Different operators have been developed for this reason, with the following being the most common ones:

$$\text{DE1: } v_i^{(t+1)} = x_g^{(t)} + F \left(x_{r_1}^{(t)} - x_{r_2}^{(t)} \right), \quad (2)$$

$$\text{DE2: } v_i^{(t+1)} = x_{r_1}^{(t)} + F \left(x_{r_2}^{(t)} - x_{r_3}^{(t)} \right), \quad (3)$$

$$\text{DE3: } v_i^{(t+1)} = x_i^{(t)} + F \left(x_g^{(t)} - x_i^{(t)} + x_{r_1}^{(t)} - x_{r_2}^{(t)} \right), \quad (4)$$

$$\text{DE4: } v_i^{(t+1)} = x_g^{(t)} + F \left(x_{r_1}^{(t)} - x_{r_2}^{(t)} + x_{r_3}^{(t)} - x_{r_4}^{(t)} \right), \quad (5)$$

$$\text{DE5: } v_i^{(t+1)} = x_{r_1}^{(t)} + F \left(x_{r_2}^{(t)} - x_{r_3}^{(t)} + x_{r_4}^{(t)} - x_{r_5}^{(t)} \right), \quad (6)$$

where t denotes the iteration counter; F is a fixed user-defined parameter; g denotes the index of the best individual in the population, i.e., the one with the lowest function value; and $r_i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, are mutually different, randomly selected indices that differ also from i . Obviously, in order to be able to apply all DE mutation operators, it must hold that $N > 5$.

After mutation, recombination is applied on the generated vector v_i , producing a *trial vector*:

$$u_i = (u_{i1}, u_{i2}, \dots, u_{in})^\top, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N,$$

as follows:

$$u_{ij}^{(t+1)} = \begin{cases} v_{ij}^{(t+1)}, & \text{if } R_j \leq CR \text{ or } j = RI(i), \\ x_{ij}^{(t)}, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$; R_j is the j -th evaluation of a uniform random number generator in the range $[0, 1]$; $CR \in [0, 1]$ is a user-defined crossover constant; and $RI(i)$ is an index randomly

selected from the set $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Finally, the best one between the produced trial vector u_i and the corresponding individual x_i , is included in the population of the next generation.

DE has proved to be very sensitive on its parameter values and operators. In the context of noisy optimization problems, the crucial issue is the safe selection of the decision vector after the recombination stage, and the safe selection of the global best point for the operators that use it in the mutation process of the next iteration. In order to reduce the effect of noise, the RL scheme described at a following section is used to increase the PCS value up to a predefined threshold.

2.2 Probability of Correct Selection

In DE, as aforementioned, there are two procedures that can seriously affect the search. In noisy problems, the challenge lies at the main task of identifying the actual best candidate with respect to the smallest mean objective function value, while minimizing the total number of replications needed for a precise selection. At this point, the *Probability of Correct Selection* is a metric that can be used.

Consider a set consist of S candidate solutions, each one already assigned a number, N_l , of replications (not necessarily equal). Let f_{lm} be the objective value of the m -th evaluation of candidate l , $l = 1, 2, \dots, S$, $m = 1, 2, \dots, M_l$. If μ_l and $\hat{\sigma}_l^2$ denote the sample mean and variance of the obtained objective values for candidate l , respectively, then:

$$\mu_l = \sum_{m=1}^{S_l} \frac{f_{lm}}{S_l}, \quad \hat{\sigma}_l^2 = \sum_{m=1}^{S_l} \frac{(f_{lm} - \bar{f}_l)^2}{(S_l - 1)}.$$

Apparently, the values of S_l , \bar{f}_l , $\hat{\sigma}_l^2$, change as long as additional replications are performed.

We assume that the means, μ_l , follow the *Student distribution*:

$$St(\bar{f}_l, M_l/\hat{\sigma}_l^2, S_l - 1).$$

Given the available replications data, Θ , the PCS_{Bayes} that the individual k with the best observed mean is the actual best, can be approximated as follows [5]:

$$\begin{aligned} PCS_{\text{Bayes}} &= P\left(\mu_k \leq \min_{l \neq k} \mu_l \mid \Theta\right) \\ &\geq \prod_{l \neq k} P(\mu_k \leq \mu_l \mid \Theta) \\ &\approx \prod_{l \neq k} \Phi_{v_{kl}}(d_{lk}/s_{lh}), \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where Φ_v is the cumulative distribution function of Student's distribution; v_{lh} are the degrees of freedom; $d_{lk} = \bar{f}_l - \bar{f}_k$ are the observed differences; and $s_{lh} = \sqrt{\hat{\sigma}_l^2/N_l + \hat{\sigma}_k^2/N_k}$, is the variance of the difference of the estimated means.

Alternatively, a set of only *good solutions* can be used, giving raise to the problem of maximizing the *Probability of Good Selection*, as defined in [6, 5].

2.3 Polynomial Extrapolation - Neville's algorithm

Neville's algorithm -closely related to *Atkin's algorithm*- is more accurate than *Lagrange's* classical formula ([9]) for polynomial interpolation and extrapolation.

Let P_1 be the value at s of the unique polynomial of degree zero passing through the point (s_1, y_1) ; thus $P_1 = y_1$. In a same manner P_2, P_3, \dots, P_Z are defined. Let P_{12} be the value at s of the unique polynomial of degree one passing through both (s_1, y_1) and (s_2, y_2) , and $P_{23}, P_{34}, \dots, P_{(Z-1)Z}$. For higher-order polynomials, up to $P_{123\dots Z}$, the value of the unique interpolating polynomial through all Z points is the desired answer. For $Z = 4$, the following tableau is formed:

$$\begin{aligned}
s_1 : y_1 &= P_1 \\
s_2 : y_2 &= P_2 \quad P_{12} \\
s_3 : y_3 &= P_3 \quad P_{123} \\
s_4 : y_4 &= P_4 \quad P_{1234} \\
&\quad P_{23} \quad P_{1234} \\
&\quad P_{34} \\
&\quad P_{234}
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Neville's algorithm is a recursive way of filling in the numbers in aforementioned tableau one column at a time, from left to right. It is based on the relationship between a "daughter" P and its two "parents", as follows: ([9]):

$$P_i(i+1) \dots (i+h) = \frac{(s - s_{i+h})P_{i(i+1)\dots(i+h-1)} + (s_i - s)P_{(i+1)(i+2)\dots(i+h)}}{s_i - s_{i+h}} \tag{10}$$

This recurrent equation is based on the agreement of the parents at points $s_{i+1} \dots s_{i+h-1}$.

2.4 Reinforcement Learning

Reinforcement Learning (RL) is a machine learning field, based on a reward maximization approach [10]. Among the numerous approaches developed in recent years, the *Parallel Recombinative Reinforcement Learning* (PRRL) technique [11–13] has been established as a population-based recombinative technique and also used for the solution of binary optimization problems. It has also been extended to its multivalued variant (MPRRL) and can tackle continuous problems with its individual optimizers, using a set of adaptable parameters, based on the *Reinforce Theorem*.

In binary problems, the scheme generates new candidate solutions, $y = (y_1, \dots, y_n)$, using a group of n Bernoulli units, each one determining a component, y_j , of the binary output vector. The MDS unit generalizes the Bernoulli unit, providing discrete output values, $y \in \{a_1, \dots, a_L\}$. Also, it is characterized by a parameter vector, $w = (w_1, \dots, w_L)$, and a corresponding probability vector, $p = (p_1, \dots, p_L)$, which is computed as follows:

$$p_i = \frac{\exp(w_i/T)}{\sum_{j=1}^L \exp(w_j/T)}, \tag{11}$$

where T is a positive control parameter. Obviously, it holds that $\sum_{i=1}^L p_i = 1$.

According to the *Reinforce Algorithms* [14], based on the stochastic hill-climbing property, the weights of an MDS unit are updated at each step according to the formula:

$$\Delta w_i = \alpha(r - \bar{r}) \frac{\partial \ln g}{\partial w_i}, \tag{12}$$

where α is the *learning rate factor*; r is the *reinforcement signal* delivered by the environment as a reward; r_{ex} is the *predicted signal* for the next stage, based on the values of the extrapolation polynomials; \bar{r} is the *reinforcement comparison*, defined as:

$$\bar{r}^{(t)} = \gamma \bar{r}^{(t-1)} + (1 - \gamma)r'^{(t)}, \tag{13}$$

where

$$r'^{(t)} = \kappa r^{(t)} + (1 - \kappa)r_{ex}^{(t+1)} \tag{14}$$

The parameter γ is a decay rate, κ is the rate of influence of the value - based on extrapolation - of the predicted reward, both in the range $[0, 1]$; and $g(a, w) = P\{y = a | w\}$ is the probability that the output y will be equal to a when the parameter vector is w . The use of the predicted values of environment signal into the reward formula is related to neuroscience models, where future rewards can be treated as rewarding themselves, acting as secondary reinforcers, and have mainly been introduced in Temporal Difference learning approaches.

Concerning the MDS unit:

$$\frac{\partial \ln g}{\partial p_i} = \begin{cases} 1/p_i, & \text{if } y = a_i, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

Moreover,

$$\frac{\partial \ln g}{\partial w_i} = \sum_{k=1}^L \frac{\partial \ln g}{\partial p_k} \frac{\partial p_k}{\partial w_i}, \quad (16)$$

and, from Eq. (11), it follows:

$$\frac{\partial p_i}{\partial w_k} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{T} p_i (1 - p_i), & \text{if } k = i, \\ -\frac{1}{T} p_i p_k, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Based on the above relations, it follows that:

$$\Delta w_i = \begin{cases} \alpha(r' - \bar{r}) \frac{1}{T} p_i (1 - p_i) - \delta w_i, & \text{if } i = k, \\ -\alpha(r' - \bar{r}) \frac{1}{T} p_i p_k - \delta w_i, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

where $-\delta w_i$ is a decay term that balances convergence, with $0 < \delta < 1$. Equation (18) is the main reinforcement update rule used in the MPRRL algorithm. This approach was also adopted in our algorithm. Further details on the MPRRL algorithm and the use of MDS units in discrete optimization environments can be found in [11].

3 The Proposed Method

As mentioned in Section 2.2, in parallel to the approach of PSO [8], the main issue for the convergence of the population to the global best point, is the correct determination of the best - according to the objective function mean values - decision vector after the mutation and recombination processes (7), as well as the correct determination of the globally best solution. We extend the approach of [8] by using prediction for RL, integrated into DE algorithm in order to allocate the computational budget in terms of function evaluations, and compare the final results with the previous approach.

Initially, consider a set of S candidate solutions as the whole population, each one already assigned a number, N_0 of fixed replications, N_p be the maximum number of replications per candidate to clarify the best between the new and the previous position, and N_g the maximum number of replications allowed for the determination of the global guide. After the random initialization of the population into the search space and the N_0 evaluations, the corresponding mean and standard deviation values are obtained, μ_{x_i} and $\hat{\sigma}_{x_i}$, as well as the extrapolated ones, $\mu_{x_i}^{(ex)}$ and $\hat{\sigma}_{x_i}^{(ex)}$, in order to be used for the derivation of PCS and PCS_{pred} values.

By the iterative optimization scheme, each member of the population x_i , after mutation and recombination performs N_0 replications and is isolated with the candidate solution of the previous iteration, let bp_i . They are assigned equal weights w_{x_i} and w_{bp_i} which are used to produce the selection probabilities as shown in Eq. (11). Probabilistic selection is performed for the next replication, based on PCS and PCS_{pred} (Eq. 8) values which are used as the reward, namely r and r_{ex} , until PCS reaches a predefined threshold or the total M_p replications have been exhausted, selecting repeatedly between x_i and bp_i . The same procedure is applied on all members of population.

The same procedure is also used for the determination of the globally optimal solution. For a fair experimental comparison with PSO, we selected mutation operators DE1, DE3 and DE4, as the rest do not use a global best point in mutation and are totally decentralized. The best positions are assigned initially equal weights and the mean and standard deviation values are obtained. Probabilistic selection takes place for the assignment of the next replication. After the replication, the corresponding mean and standard deviation values along with the extrapolated ones for the selected candidate, and the PCS and predicted PCS are used for the computation of the new weights according to the RL rules.

As already reported in [8] regarding the probabilistic selection, two schemes are considered, namely *Stochastic Independent Decisions* (SID) and the well known *Roulette Wheel* (RW) selection. The first one individually examines each candidate, either selecting or neglecting it, based on its probability.

Fig. 1: Statistical comparison tests among the algorithms.

4 Experimental Results

4.1 Experimental Setting

We have performed multiple experiments and statistical comparisons for the two methods as reported in Fig 1. Statistical comparisons are based on the Wilcoxon ranksum test, for positive, equal or negative comparison with statistical significance. The three variants of DE were compared with the PSO variants, for different noise levels, dimension sizes and selection algorithm (RL-RW). Specifically, noise levels of 0.01, 0.03 and 0.05 were used as a representative range. The problems already reported in [8], namely the Sphere, the Generalized Rosenbrock, Rastrigin, Griewank and Ackley functions, were used with dimensionality of 5, 15 and 40, as representative for the comparison.

4.2 Results Analysis

By examining Fig 1a, a declining trend is observed in PSO positive comparisons offering an advantage for DE3 and DE4, while with DE1 the most equal comparisons are reported. DE3 stands well enough in the comparison with PSO, taking into account the equal tests. Hence it is shown that as the number of mutation operator members increases, the performance of the algorithm reports more positive comparisons of DE against PSO, with DE4 completely outperforming PSO. It should also be noted that equal results are increased for DE1 and decline for DE3, DE4, promoting DE.

In Fig 1b a detailed comparison between DE1 and PSO is reported. In this case PSO shows better results against DE1 operator in all cases of dimensions selection and noise levels. Some cases of positive comparisons arise for DE, mostly for the RW selection option. The RW selection also outperforms the simple computational budget selection in PSO, appearing as a good selection alternative for population members in the algorithms.

Fig 1c presents the results for DE3, where the algorithm shows improved behaviour in low dimensionality and in high noise levels. In general, an increased number of positive comparisons appear for DE3 performance, however only for RW selection scenarios. DE3 operator with the simple selection mechanism shows some positive results only for low dimensionality and high noise, following the trend of DE with RW, which appears as a decent competitor to the corresponding PSO variants.

Finally, in Fig 1d, DE4 operator with RW selection shows definitely improved results with more positive comparisons against all variants of PSO algorithm, for all cases of noise levels and dimensionality selection. In this scenario, a slightly better performance is shown also for the simple DE4 selection mechanism, compared to the other operators.

This behaviour of DE could be explained with two main arguments: firstly, the increased number of population members in mutation operator, which increases performance of the algorithm and secondly, the advanced RW selection mechanism which allocates intelligently the available computational budget to promising solutions and thus decreases the effect of noise. It should also be noted that performance of DE operators in the cases that PSO shows more positive comparisons, is not negligible, as most of the rest of the comparisons are on equal state. Further experimentation with DE operators can be shown for the selection of the values for F and CR parameters, which fine-tune the behaviour of the algorithm.

5 Conclusions

In this paper we presented a new hybrid variant of Differential Evolution algorithm, which was supplemented with a Reinforcement Learning and Polynomial Extrapolation mechanism in order to solve difficult optimization problems with noise. We presented extended experiments along with a comparison with a Particle Swarm Optimization counterpart and analytical results, as a new algorithm is included to the set of powerful algorithms for the difficult cases of noisy problems. We have shown that this variant of hybridized Differential Evolution can cope with uncertainty efficiently in benchmark problems. Further experimentation may release the complete advantages of the algorithm and fine-tune its performance on both benchmark functions and real applications.

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